

Reconstruction of the helium to proton flux ratio in galactic cosmic rays using neutron monitor data

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Abstract

This paper presents a multiple linear regression framework for reconstructing the historical helium-to-proton (He/p) flux ratio of galactic cosmic rays (GCRs) leveraging long-term, ground-based neutron monitor datasets. Optimized via a Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm, the model was calibrated and trained on direct satellite measurements from PAMELA and AMS-02 covering the period 2006–2019 and was subsequently applied to estimate the He/p ratio for the extended period of 1980–2019. The reconstruction results show good agreement when validated against independent historical data from balloon-borne e

xperiments. Given that the He/p ratio is a crucial indicator of cosmic ray modulation, utilizing the extensive time coverage of the neutron monitor network provides deeper insights into solar modulation dynamics over past solar cycles.

Keywords

cosmic rays, neutron monitors, solar cycle

Introduction

Galactic cosmic rays (GCRs) are high-energy charged particles originating outside the solar system, consisting predominantly of protons and helium nuclei. During the heliospheric transport process, these particles interact with the solar wind and the heliospheric magnetic field. This interaction causes long-term variations in GCR fluxes, a phenomenon known as the heliospheric modulation of cosmic rays. The extent of its influence is determined by the phase of the 11-year solar cycle (Potgieter 2013). While solar maximum is characterized by high solar activity and an increased number of sunspots, solar minimum is marked by low solar activity and a minimal sunspot count. Consequently, during solar maxima, enhanced modulation processes significantly weaken the fluxes of particles with rigidities below a certain threshold.

Conversely, during solar minima, this threshold decreases, allowing a higher flux of lower-rigidity particles to penetrate the heliosphere. The transport and modulation of GCRs are formally described by the Parker equation (Moraal 2013) for the distribution function $f(r,p,t)$:

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K}^{(s)} \cdot \nabla f) - \mathbf{v}_d \cdot \nabla f - \mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla f + \frac{1}{3} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{V} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p},$$

where $\mathbf{K}^{(s)}$ is the symmetric part of the diffusion tensor, describing the interaction with the heliospheric magnetic field, \mathbf{V} is the solar wind speed, and \mathbf{v}_d is the drift velocity. This equation cannot be solved analytically, so forward or backward propagation codes (e.g., HelMod Online calculator 2025) are used to reconstruct the modulation pattern. Direct fluxes of protons and helium nuclei registered by satellite detectors are used to validate numerical models. However, continuous satellite records span only the

recent 2006–2019 period, following the deployment of the PAMELA (Adriani et al. 2017) and AMS-02 (Aguilar 2021) experiments. Consequently, validating numerical models for earlier solar cycles requires alternative boundary conditions, such as the He/p flux ratio (Zhu 2024). This paper introduces a regression-based approach that leverages ground-based neutron monitor data to reconstruct historical He/p ratios over several decades.

Neutron monitor data

Despite the decades of operation, ground-based neutron monitors (NMs; Simpson 2012) remain an essential tool for studying cosmic ray fluxes. The global network employs two standardized types of detectors: IGY (Hughes and Marsden 1966) and NM64 (Hatton and Carimichael 1964). Although these configurations differ in their structural geometry and counting efficiency, both designs share a similar primary response profile. Consequently, these neutron monitors are most sensitive to cosmic rays with energies in the range of 0.5–20 GeV (Asvestari et al. 2017), which corresponds to the energy range where heliospheric modulation effects are most pronounced. A standard neutron monitor consists of central proportional counter tubes filled with gas (traditionally boron trifluoride, BF₃, enriched with ¹⁰B, or Helium-3, ³He) enclosed by three distinct functional layers: a moderator, a heavy lead radiator, and an outer reflector. The detection process operates as a sequential physical chain. First, secondary hadrons (primarily protons and neutrons) produced by the interaction of cosmic rays with the Earth's atmosphere arrive at the detector. They pass through the outer reflector, which shields the system by blocking low-energy environmental neutrons from entering. These high-energy atmospheric particles then strike the heavy lead radiator, inducing nuclear spallation and evaporation reactions that generate a multiplicity of low-energy neutrons. Next, these newly produced neutrons enter the inner moderator, where elastic collisions slow them down to thermal energies. Finally, these thermalized neutrons diffuse into the proportional counter tubes, causing gas ionization and triggering measurable electrical pulses.

The registration of cosmic rays by ground-based networks is governed by two sequential filtering mechanisms: geomagnetic shielding and atmospheric attenuation. First, primary particles must penetrate the Earth's magnetosphere, a process dictated by their magnetic rigidity ($R = pc/Ze$), where p is the particle's momentum, c is the speed of light, Z is the atomic number (nuclear charge), and e is the elementary charge. Rigidity measures a particle's resistance to magnetic deflection. This geomagnetic shielding varies continuously across the globe, with the cutoff rigidity reaching its maximum near the equator and dropping toward zero near the poles. Consequently, any ground-based neutron monitor station can only register cosmic rays that possess enough rigidity to penetrate the magnetosphere at its specific geographic

coordinate. For a given station, this local shielding threshold is quantified as the effective cutoff rigidity (R_{eff}), which physically defines the minimum rigidity a primary particle must possess to contribute to the neutron monitor's count rate. Alongside the geomagnetic barrier, the primary particles must simultaneously overcome the material barrier of the Earth's atmosphere, where they collide with air nuclei to initiate secondary atmospheric cascades (Cooke et al. 1991). The fraction of secondary hadrons generated within these cascades that successfully reaches the ground to be registered by neutron monitors depends heavily on the atmospheric depth at the station's location and the primary particle's energy. For instance, if the primary proton energy is insufficient (below approximately 400 MeV), the resulting shower fails to penetrate down to the Earth's surface (Mishev and Poluianov 2021) at Earth poles regions. Furthermore, the total NM count rate is influenced by the varying contribution of primary heavy nuclei ($Z \geq 2$), mostly helium. Because these heavier particles initiate atmospheric showers differently than protons, they fundamentally alter how the secondary cascade develops.

Satellite experiment data

In this study, we utilized data from two space-borne experiments: PAMELA and AMS-02, whose measurements of proton and helium nuclei fluxes cover the period from 2006 to 2019. The PAMELA mission marked a major milestone as the first long-duration, large-scale magnetic spectrometer deployed in space. Launched in June 2006 onboard the Resurs-DK1 satellite, it provided continuous, high-precision measurements of cosmic ray fluxes for over a decade, effectively ushering in the era of modern space-borne particle spectroscopy. This trajectory of high-precision space-borne research was continued by the AMS-02 magnetic spectrometer, installed on the International Space Station in May 2011. Conceptually building upon the detector configuration of its predecessor, AMS-02 is a next-generation, high-precision particle detector. It consists of several detector systems: a tracker inside a superconducting magnet, a time-of-flight system, Cherenkov counters, an electromagnetic calorimeter, and an anticoincidence counter system. The superconducting magnet bends the trajectories of charged particles, allowing the spectrometer to measure their magnetic rigidity and precisely distinguish charged cosmic rays from neutral particles. These advanced technical capabilities, combined with over a decade of continuous operation in space, allow AMS-02 to record long-term variations in GCR fluxes with unprecedented precision and high temporal resolution.

In this work, we utilized proton and helium nuclei flux data from both experiments within a rigidity range of 1–100 GV. The dataset comprises Bartels rotation-averaged (27-day) data from the PAMELA experiment covering the 2006–2011 period (Adriani et al. 2013; Martucci

et al. 2018; Marcelli et al. 2020, 2022), complemented by high-resolution daily data from AMS-02 spanning 2011–2019 (Aguilar et al. 2021, 2022).

Data preparation: neutron monitors

The multiple linear regression model used in this study requires highly continuous data across a diverse network of different neutron monitors. This multi-station approach is essential because the regression algorithm relies on comparing the simultaneous, unique responses of various stations—dictated by their local cutoff rigidities and altitudes—to isolate the primary He/p ratio signatures from general flux intensity variations. Furthermore, since the model operates on a daily time resolution over a multi-decade span, maintaining strict data continuity is critical; any simultaneous gaps across the network reduce the effective size of the training vector or introduce interpolation errors. However, expanding the network creates a clear trade-off: as the number of included NMs increases, the total volume of missing data grows, potentially degrading regression performance. Conversely, restricting the analysis to a small number of stations prevents the model from exploiting these station-specific variations in count rates, thereby limiting its overall accuracy.

To select neutron monitors with the most continuous data, we employed the following method. The count rate data from all monitors were divided into two parts: a training set (after 2006) and a test set (before 2006). For each monitor, the percentage of missing days in both parts of the dataset was calculated. If this percentage exceeded 15% in either part, the monitor was excluded from further analysis. The 15% threshold was chosen empirically, as it provided an optimal balance between the number of remaining monitors and the reliability of their data.

Once the final set of monitors was established, their hourly pressure-corrected count rate data were smoothed via a 14-day moving average, effectively filtering out diurnal variations and short-term transient phenomena (Cane 2000) and highlighting the underlying long-term modulation trends (Fig. 1). Missing data points were filled using a combination of linear interpolation and noise injection. This technique, widely used as a method for stochastic imputation and data augmentation, preserves the realistic high-frequency variance of the neutron monitor count rates and acts as a regularizer, preventing the SGD regressor from overfitting to artificially smoothed data intervals (Bishop 1995; Little and Rubin 2002). The final set of monitors and their characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. List of neutron monitors used in this study and the characteristics of their locations

Name	Geomagnetic cutoff rigidity (GV)	Atmospheric depth (g/cm ²)
TSMB	8.95	880
SOPO	0.1	680
NEWK	2.4	1013
HRMS	4.44	1013.25
JUNG	4.49	642.614
KERG	1.14	1000
OULU	0.62	1000
THUL	0.3	1005

Data preparation: satellite data

The PAMELA dataset utilized in this study provides Bartels rotation-averaged (27-day) proton and helium nuclei fluxes. To ensure temporal alignment with the daily resolution of AMS-02 and maintain consistency within

Figure 1. Dependence of neutron monitor count rates on time averaged over 14 days; the legend lists the names of the neutron monitors in the same order (top to bottom) as on the graph.

the regression framework, the PAMELA data were up-sampled to a daily resolution via linear interpolation. While higher-order interpolation methods (such as cubic splines) are available, a linear approach was selected to prevent the introduction of unphysical numerical artifacts. Non-linear interpolation can cause overshooting or artificial oscillations between the 27-day averages, particularly during periods of volatile solar activity. Linear interpolation serves as a conservative constraint that preserves the monotonic trend of heliospheric modulation between measured intervals without injecting artificial high-order features that could lead to overfitting within the regression framework. To prevent this interpolation from creating artificially smoothed intervals that could bias the SGD optimization, a small stochastic noise component—scaled to 10% of the flux standard deviation—was injected into the reconstructed time series. This stochastic data augmentation preserves realistic high-frequency variance across the entire training dataset, as illustrated in the left panel of Fig. 2. The justification for this approach was demonstrated using AMS-02 data, which were averaged over Bartels rotations (27 days) to mimic the resolution constraints of the PAMELA dataset, and then linearly interpolated with stochastic noise scaled to 10% of the flux standard deviation. The results are presented in the right panel of Fig. 2. As can be seen, they agree well with the actual daily AMS-02 data within error margins, confirming the validity of applying this method to the PAMELA data. Although the simulated daily data exhibit a slightly smaller statistical spread (variance) compared to the real daily measurements due to the smoothing effect of the initial 27-day averaging, this discrepancy fundamentally stems from their differing statistical natures. The experimental fluxes compiled from spectrometer measurements inherently contain high-frequency statistical fluctuations, short-term solar transient variations, and instrument-specific systematic uncertainties. Conversely, the regression framework acts as a regularized statistical filter optimized to track the central tendency of the physical flux. By smoothing out non-physical, high-frequency measurement noise, the model avoids overfitting instrumental scatter and accurately reproduces the underlying long-term heliospheric modulation trends required for the reconstruction.

Reconstruction of He/p flux ratio

Reconstructing the flux ratio (He/p) rather than individual absolute fluxes offers a compelling methodological advantage, particularly when cross-validating results across disparate experimental missions. While absolute flux measurements from different satellite and balloon-borne instruments frequently exhibit systematic shifts caused by instrument-specific geometric factors, tracking efficiencies, or atmospheric correction uncertainties, taking the ratio of these components effectively mitigates these discrepancies. Because common-mode systematic errors largely

cancel out within the same experimental framework, the He/p ratio provides a highly robust, self-calibrated observable uniquely suited for multi-experiment trend analysis.

Using this approach, a regression function was established on the training dataset to map the correlation between ground-based neutron monitor count rates and the primary He/p ratio for particle kinetic energies up to 20 GeV/nucleon. Although ground-based neutron monitors detect only secondary particles produced in atmospheric cascades, their combined count rates are implicitly sensitive to the primary He/p ratio due to two interconnected physical phenomena: geomagnetic/atmospheric filtration and species-specific yield functions, both of which are mathematically formalized in modern neutron monitor yield functions (Mishev et al. 2020). First, for a given magnetic rigidity R , a helium nucleus carries approximately half the kinetic energy per nucleon of a proton due to its mass-to-charge ratio ($A/Z = 2$). Second, since the development of an atmospheric shower heavily depends on the energy per nucleon, primary protons and helium nuclei at the same rigidity possess significantly different specific yield functions ($Y_p(R) \neq Y_{He}(R)$). Consequently, variations in the primary He/p ratio differentially affect the count rates of various stations across the global network depending on their local cutoff rigidities (R_c) and atmospheric depths (h). This multi-variable dependency creates a high-dimensional, non-linear mapping that cannot be adequately captured or represented by a simplified bivariate time-series correlation with any single detector. Instead, by utilizing the collective multi-station matrix calibrated against direct satellite measurements, the regression model successfully exploits these distinct, synchronized responses. This data-driven approach implicitly bypasses the inherent degeneracies of analytical yield-function inversion and automatically filters out station-specific environmental anomalies, effectively unraveling the multi-variable network data to robustly reconstruct the long-term historical dynamics of the primary He/p ratio.

To analyze the helium-to-proton ratio (He/p) in GCR fluxes, we employed Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) from the Python scikit-learn library. This method is based on minimizing a loss function, in this case, the mean squared error (MSE) between the actual values y and the predicted values $f(x)$, where $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is the input vector of variables. The goal of the method is to find a model that approximates the dependence $f(x) = b_0 + b_1x_1 + \dots + b_nx_n$, minimizing the difference between $f(x)$ and y by adjusting the weights b_0, b_1, \dots, b_n . SGD is a modification of classical gradient descent. Its key difference lies in the fact that the gradient of the loss function is computed not over the entire dataset but over a small randomly selected subset (mini-batch). This significantly speeds up the learning process, especially when working with large datasets, as it reduces the number of computations per iteration. However, due to the use of random subsets, the optimization process can be less stable, but with proper tuning of parameters (e.g., learning rate), SGD demonstrates high efficiency.

Figure 2. (upper panel) Dependence of helium nuclei fluxes on time for real and interpolated data from PAMELA and AMS-02. (middle panel) Dependence of proton fluxes on time for real and interpolated data from PAMELA and AMS-02. (lower panel) Dependence of the helium-to-proton (He/p) flux ratio on time for real and interpolated data from PAMELA and AMS-02.

The selection of the specific functional form for the regression was governed by both physical and statistical considerations. First, the method must be capable of mapping the non-linear, threshold-dependent relationships imposed by geomagnetic cutoffs and atmospheric cascade development. Second, because the count rates from different stations across the global network are highly

correlated, the fitting procedure must maintain numerical stability to avoid overfitting local instrumental noise. Ultimately, the parameters of the regression function were determined by minimizing the root-mean-square error (RMSE) on the calibration dataset, which covers the period of direct satellite observations (PAMELA and AMS-02) overlapping with the neutron monitor records.

The definitive criterion for selection was the maximization of the model's generalization capacity, ensuring stable predictive performance across different epochs of solar activity. Furthermore, since this work represents a pioneering attempt to reconstruct the historical He/p ratio directly from ground-based multi-station records, establishing a robust, transparent, and well-characterized baseline was prioritized. Utilizing a foundational regression approach ensures interpretability and provides a necessary reference performance level before more complex architectures can be meaningfully explored in future studies.

This function was then applied to the test set of NM count rates, and the coefficients of determination R^2 were calculated between the actual and computed He/p values. The graph of R^2 as a function of kinetic energy per nucleon is shown in Fig. 3. The coefficient of determination is calculated using the following formula:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - f(x_i))^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

where y_i are the actual values, $f(x_i)$ are the predicted values, and \bar{y} is the mean of the actual values.

Figure 3. Dependence of the coefficient of determination (R^2) of the final model on verification data as a function of the kinetic energy per nucleon of the particles.

From the graph in Fig. 3, it is evident that the highest correlation is observed for relatively low energies per nucleon, after which the correlation decreases. This higher accuracy in the low-energy region is attributed to both the peak physical sensitivity of the neutron monitor network in this range and the significantly larger statistical weight of the experimental data, as galactic cosmic ray fluxes drop sharply with increasing energy following a power-law spectrum. The maximum coefficient of determination R^2 , equal to 0.91, is observed at a kinetic energy per nucleon of 2.33 GeV/nucleon. Data from balloon and spectrometer experiments that measured proton and helium nuclei fluxes were used to verify the final results: BESS (Seo et al. 2001; Shikaze et al. 2007; Wang et al. 2008; Abe et al. 2015), AMS-01 (Alcaraz et al. 2000a; Alcaraz et al. 2000b), IMAX (Menn 2000), LEAP (Seo et al. 1991), and CAPRICE (Boezio et al. 1999). These missions were carried out by different international collaborations across multiple launch sites and locations, including Fort Sumner (USA), Lynn Lake (Canada), ESRANGE (Sweden), McMurdo Station (Antarctica), and low Earth orbit. Although the individual payloads featured distinct sensor configurations—utilizing varying combinations of superconducting magnets, gas drift chambers, and time-of-flight counters—they shared a common objective. The balloon campaigns operated at high stratospheric altitudes of approximately 35–40 km (corresponding to a minimal residual atmospheric depth of 3–5 g/cm²), providing precise, direct measurements of primary proton and helium spectra above the bulk of the Earth's atmosphere.

The reconstructed He/p flux ratio, illustrated in Fig. 4, exhibits good agreement with historical balloon-borne measurements, thereby validating the robustness of the proposed framework. Extensive hyperparameter tuning yielded no significant improvement in either the coefficient of determination (R^2) or the model's alignment with the experimental balloon data. Consequently, the default hyperparameter configuration of the Stochastic Gradient

Figure 4. Dependence of the reconstructed He/p ratio on time for an energy of 2.33 GeV/nucleon.

Descent (SGD) regressor from the scikit-learn library was retained for the final architecture.

Conclusion

In this study, a multiple linear regression framework optimized via the Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) algorithm was successfully developed to reconstruct the historical galactic cosmic ray helium-to-proton (He/p ratio) at an energy of 2.33 GeV/nucleon over the multi-decade period of 1980–2019. The reconstructed profiles exhibit strong alignment not only with the space-borne data (PAMELA and AMS-02) used for model training but also with independent historical balloon-borne experiments (BESS, IMAX, AMS-01, LEAP, and CAPRICE) utilized strictly for cross-validation. While heliospheric transport

and cosmic ray modulation are inherently non-linear processes governed by complex drift and diffusion mechanisms, our results demonstrate that a linearized multi-station regression approach provides a highly reliable first-order approximation. This simplified model successfully captures the coherent modulation signals embedded within ground-based neutron monitor networks to isolate species-dependent variations. As a pioneering attempt to bridge the gap between long-term ground observations and high-precision satellite spectrometry, this work establishes a robust baseline. Future advancements will focus on relaxing current model assumptions by implementing non-linear machine learning architectures, such as artificial neural networks, and expanding the reconstruction framework across a broader rigidity spectrum to account more dynamically for charge-sign and mass-dependent modulation effects.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) Use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Both authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.
